

Tutoring As A New Branch Of Teaching In Uzbekistan Education System

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ABSTRACT

This article describes the introduction of "tutoring" into the educational system of Uzbekistan, the development of this process, and various opinions and concepts in the field of tutoring by tutoring scholars. Through this, tutors and future personnels in this field can acquire the most necessary knowledge about tutoring for themselves.

Keywords: tutoring, goal, motivation, trait, student personality, republic, education system, goal-oriented and practical, skill, attitude.

Determining the priorities for the systematic reform of higher education in our republic, raising the process of training highly qualified personnel with modern knowledge and high spiritual and moral qualities to a qualitatively new level, modernizing higher education, developing social sphere and economic sectors based on educational technologies is one of the important tasks in these days. In order to solve these tasks, the introduction of "tutoring" activities in higher education institutions of the Uzbekistan republic will strengthen the relationship between the university and students in organizing the education and training process. Besides this, it helps students adapting to university's life and the educational process, and serves to provide social, pedagogical-psychological support and develop students' love for their profession.

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approval of the concept in terms of developing higher education system in the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" dated October 8, 2019 No. PF-5847 and the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Higher Education "On measures to improve the system related to the organization of the educational process in educational institutions" on December 31, 2020 No. 824 and September 9, 2021 No. 563 and in order to determine the directions and regulations on the organization of tutoring activities in state higher education institutions has been put into practice.

Teaching In Uzbekistan Education System.

Worth Noting:

• According to Russian pedagogues I. V. Karpenkova and E. V. Kuzmina, "Tutoring is a practice, and activity that is designed for taking into account the strategy of personal education, the construction, the personal potential of a person, the infrastructure and the implementation of social tasks".

• Based on A.N. Bogachev's research, he concludes: "Tutoring is an individual educational program which is designed to individualize education directed at learners and to create the phenomenon and development of educational motives and interests".

• Based on A.V. Aleksandrova's research, he comments on the tutoring activity: "A tutor or any teacher that performing tutoring functions, works as a guide of the learner in the field of education at the initial stages of training."

Among them, starting from November 1, 2021, instead of the institute of "group coach" for working with students at Fergana State University the practice of "tutors" working with students was introduced.

There are several conceptions about "tutoring" and here you can some of them. According to Russian pedagogues I. V. Karpenkova and E. V. Kuzmina, "Tutoring is a practice, and activity that is designed for taking into account the strategy of personal education, the construction, the personal potential of a person, the infrastructure and the implementation of social tasks".

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American scientist, psychologist, humanist Carl Ransom Rodgers explains the status of a tutor as follows:

"The tutor is:
- teacher;
- mediator;
- a person who teaches independent decision-making in the field of education;

- a person who supports the educational process".

"Tutoring is a profession that takes a supportive position in the educational environment, seeks for self-education, an individual educational environment, and develops the culture of education and upbringing in parallel." (A. Maslow, F. Perlz, E. Shostrom).

In other words, a tutor is represented as a person who produces an educational product that could not be measured by any "customized" standards and, in general, could not be produced in the same way by another tutor.

Currently, tutoring activity in higher education institutions of our Republic is gradually getting mixed with the education system. We have a

number of shortcomings in this field, and it will take time to correct the shortcomings, and we believe that in the future tutoring activities will become an integral part of the higher education system of the Republic and the life of students.

Muhammadjonova Madinabonu was born in 16 of March 2003 in Uzbekistan. Currently, she is studying in master's degree in faculty of Pedagogical Theory and History in Fergana State University. she is really active person, therefore she has been participating in different kind of educational olympiads and competitions since her childhood. After the graduation the school years, she began to study in English faculty of Kokand State Pedagogical Institute. She has three-year experience in teaching and tutoring. In the future she wants to share all her knowledge in terms of English and its usage and also the secrets of teaching pupils and students. Developing the education system of Uzbekistan is one of her biggest dreams.